

Machine Learning-Statistics Ensemble Battery EOL Prediction Model

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Abstract

Prediction of Lithium-ion battery end-of-life (EOL, commonly defined as capacity dropping below 80% of nominal) is a condition-based maintenance (CBM) problem with wide application in industry. A joint team from MIT and Stanford conducted accelerated life testing experiments on 124 LFP/graphite batteries; they and others have generated additional features and constructed EOL models, identifying particularly predictive features and achieving high accuracies. In this work, we examine the effects of adding more features, fitting data to fundamental functional forms, employing properties of a derivative, and applying routine statistical operations and other relevant methods on the accuracy of the resulting ensemble model in accurately predicting EOL early in cycle life.

Key Words:

ensemble, battery, RUL, EOL, curve-fitting, weighted average

1. Introduction

Understanding battery longevity has a wide range of applications across industries making it an important condition-based maintenance (CBM) problem. Accurate prediction of battery remaining useful life (RUL) aids in reducing downtime and maintenance costs. It is fundamental in reducing costs associated with energy storage systems, for example, and accelerates the development of energy storage technologies by providing insights into battery performance and behavior over time. Reliable predictions avoid further costs by enabling anticipatory planning to expedite the schedule and delivery of battery and other critical machine parts, thereby foregoing snarls otherwise tying up supply chains.

A large body of research devoted to this issue is found in the literature, including an impressive diversity of approaches. To name just a few: an attempt at understanding the underlying physics, electrochemical reactions, and degradation mechanisms of batteries [1]; state-space models representing the current state, and projecting the next state, of a measured battery quantity [2]; data-driven models employing statistical analysis of battery data and/or machine-learning algorithms to predict RUL directly [3, 4]; or various hybrid approaches combining multiple methodologies to enhance prediction accuracy.

A joint team [4] of researchers from MIT and Stanford conducted experiments on 124 batteries (of the APR18650M1A model), subjecting them to rapid charging and discharging cycles. In total, 72 distinct fast-charging policies were assigned, while each discharge cycle was kept uniform. In their subsequent machine-learning analysis, up to 20 features were employed in a few different models for use in studying classification and regression tasks. For the former, batteries were classified at an early cycle as to whether they would be “long-lasting” (i.e., cycle life of at least 550) or not; for the latter, an elastic net model predicted, at 100 cycles, the exact cycle at which the end-of-life (EOL) threshold was to be reached.

Some researchers [3] at Arizona State University expanded on the work of the MIT-Stanford team on this dataset by adding 11 features and applying an ensemble of machine-learning models (k -Nearest Neighbors, SVM, Random Forest, Neural Net, AdaBoost) for the above-mentioned classification task. Their approach at the corresponding regression task used a support vector regressor (SVR); some improved results were achieved.

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This work builds somewhat upon the ensemble concept in [3] by applying one to the regression task. We include an additional feature while grouping predictions from a similar SVR in a weighted average with predictions given by curve fits of functional forms. We further improve our predictions by using a mathematical derivative property to alter one functional form to obtain a greater fit. References to batteries herein are to those of the same model, and subject to the same treatment, as those studied in [4].

Figure 1: Capacity decay profiles for selected batteries.

2. Our Experiment & Work

Fig. 1 shows capacity decay profiles from the data given by [4]. The definition of EOL as typically found in the literature is 80% of nominal capacity, or 0.88 Ahr in the case of the batteries used in this dataset; these curves thus all end at that threshold. Note that they tend to have a similar shape, suggesting there may be a basic mathematical function that could serve as a model thereof to a high degree of accuracy. We fitted five families of functions to the data (see Table 1; further explanation regarding the choice for some of these particular expressions and symbols is provided in Section 3.2). Here, x represents the cycle number.

Function Family Name	Formula
Exponential	$y_0 e^{bx} + c$
Logistic	$\frac{cy_0}{ky_0 + (c - ky_0)e^{-cx}}$
Reciprocal	$\frac{y_0}{1 + ky_0x}$
Inverse Square	$\frac{-a}{(x - c)^2} + b$
Polynomial degree 3 (cubic)	$ax^3 + bx^2 + cx + d$

Table 1: Function families and their forms.

These families were chosen because of how closely their basic graphs, with the necessary transformations, align with the capacity decay curves. When including capacity data from the full range of cycles, the function families do indeed fit well, as suggested by high r^2 values. The cubic fit, however, is manifestly distinct from the others; we found that it also performs terribly in its early-cycle predictions of EOL, and we thus excluded it from the final model. Possibly a higher-degree polynomial would give a better fit; we chose, however, not to pursue this kind of fit any further.

Fig. 2 shows predictions of cycle life, adjusted as data were accumulated for some function families, as applied to one particular battery. These are hopelessly off before there are sufficient data to which the curve is fit. There is therefore a balance to be struck here: more capacity data are needed, necessitating predictions at a later cycle; however, the earlier the cycle when predictions are made, the better. We therefore need a cycle at which the cost of extra data can still be borne and yet predictions can be comparatively accurate with respect to the literature. We chose the 350th as our prediction cycle, simply because it is a “round” number and is fairly optimal, for this dataset and these methods, in considering these factors. For some battery RUL applications, predictions updated after additional data are acquired (e.g., while using a particle filter) may be considered worth the wait.

Figure 2: Predictions for selected regressors, updated as data accumulate. Dashed horizontal lines indicate $\pm 5\%$ and 10% error.

Three of the batteries reached EOL before the 350th cycle and were subsequently discarded from our analysis. One may thus expect a proportion of about three in 124 batteries would fail before predictions using the technique described in this work could be made.

Predictions tend to be better using some type of average of the function fits. In an attempt to improve upon results from [3], we included an SVR in this average. We applied cross-validation functions such as `GridSearch` from Python’s `sklearn` to tune our SVR’s hyperparameters, concluding on setting kernel to “rbf,” C to 10,000, and ϵ to 10.

A feature exhibited in Fig. 2b of [4] shows that the cycle life (represented by color) generally increases as the feature is increased. This feature, $Q_{100} - Q_{10}$ (the difference in battery capacity between the 10th and 100th cycles), thus appears to be a fairly accurate

Figure 3: 20% error cone (dashed lines) of predictions v. observations.

predictor of battery cycle life. We elected to also include the area under this curve as a new feature, along with the other seven used by [3] in their top-performing SVR.

3. Initial Results & Attempts to Improve Predictions

Because of the aforementioned three discarded batteries, the training and test sets are changed from Severson et al.’s original indexing. Training and test sets were thus randomly reshuffled, giving differing results from the SVR, and subsequently the average, for each run. Our initial results for the averages described in the previous section gave an average percent error of 10.5%, better than the averages of respective models in [3]’s Table 3 of results. Root mean squared error (RMSE), however, averages out at just over 200, which is worse than any of [3]’s. As seen in a sample “cone” of 20% percent error (Fig. 3), most of our predictions are reasonably accurate except for those eight batteries lasting more than 1500 cycles, which drastically skew the RMSE metric. Their longer life may be partially due to charge policy, which we will consider later. We now describe how we attempted to improve our predictions.

3.1 The Exponential Function Family

For this family of functions, data were translated to eliminate the constant term and instead fit functions of the form $y = y_0 e^{b(x)}$, to take advantage of the fact that, when its derivative is divided by the function, the result is the derivative of the exponent; i.e.,

$$\frac{y'}{y} = \frac{y_0 e^{b(x)} b'(x)}{y_0 e^{b(x)}} = b'(x).$$

(Of necessity, y_0 is assumed to be negative.) We therefore focus on $b'(x)$ through graphs of y'/y for each battery. If this quantity were constant, a basic exponential function (such as in Table 1) would fit the capacity decay curve. Evidence seen in the sample graphs of Fig. 4 (displaying examples of $b'(x)$ along with corresponding capacity decay curves), however, shows that $b'(x)$ is clearly not constant, so we approximate it as described below.

Please note that the fundamental calculus definition of derivative was not used for our purposes. We instead monitored values of the difference quotient

$$\frac{f(x + \Delta x) - f(x)}{\Delta x}$$

Figure 4: $b'(x)$ (blue) against capacity decay (red) for selected batteries.

for varying values of Δx . Dividing these by the original function $f(x)$ thus produced representations of $b'(x)$ all having similar shape; setting $\Delta x = 50$ cycles gave a “clean” curve (i.e., with minimal noise) that yet suggested a reasonable rate of change for the exponent, such that we could work with adequately to make predictions. We observed little difference in our results when tweaking the size of this “step” for the derivative.

Some observations of graphs of $b'(x)$, such as those in Fig. 4, include that for the first several hundred cycles, $b'(x)$ tends to be approximately linear. This ends at a certain as-yet-undetermined threshold (t_1), when $b'(x)$ begins to increase faster until reaching a “peak” several times higher than the average value of those first several hundred cycles. Afterwards, it begins decreasing, perhaps receding to a state of equilibrium, “mirroring” its earlier increase for a time up to the EOL event.

This serves as a rough outline for an automated construction of a crude sequence of connected line segments combining to approximate $b'(x)$. We can then use this approximation to estimate $b(x)$ itself, and thus in turn the capacity decay via the function $y_0 e^{b(x)}$, with the objective of an improved prediction (for the exponential function family) of the cycle number corresponding to EOL. Algorithm 1 outlines the construction of this approximation to $b'(x)$. To clarify what is meant by the “while” statement, if at any time during the construction process the EOL threshold is reached, the construction terminates and the remainder of the current line segment and any further line segments are discarded. For any battery lasting beyond the cycle of prediction, then, the number of line segments in the approximation of $b'(x)$ can be any integer from one to four. While these instructions may seem arbitrary, please recall our disclaimer of a “crude” approximation, based off observations of the graphs of $b'(x)$, as mentioned earlier.

As is evident from this discussion, and seen in Algorithm 1, integral to these approximations is the estimation of the “peaks.” We now turn to this task.

Algorithm 1: Construct approximation to $b'(x)$

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1 Begin with the capacity as measured at the cycle when the predictions will be made (the 350th, in
  our work). At this point,  $x \neq 0$ , but this selection will nevertheless determine the “ $y_0$ ” in  $y_0 e^{b(x)}$ .
2 Omitting battery “break-in” data, an initial period during which the capacity rises as the battery is
  being “broken in” (see, for example, [2, 5]; assumed in our work to be the first 50 cycles), find the
  linear least-squares fit (call it  $\ell$ ) to the remaining cycles up to the cycle of prediction.
3 while EOL threshold (80% nominal capacity) has not yet been reached do
4   Begin the first line segment at the last  $y$ -value of  $\ell$  and terminate it at the cycle at which the
  approximation for the capacity reaches a predetermined first threshold ( $t_1$ ).
5   if the “peak” is predicted to occur before  $t_1$  is reached, or if  $t_1$  is reached before the cycle of
  prediction then
6     “go straight to the peak:” set  $t_1$  to be at the point where the first line segment begins (so that
  the first line segment consists of a single point); continue with the second line segment.
7   else
8     if  $\ell$ 's slope is positive then
9       the slope of the first line segment will be that of  $\ell$ 's;
10    else
11      the slope of the first line segment will be 0.
12    end
13  end
14  The second line segment connects the end of the first to the prediction of the peak (both its
  location and value).
15  The third line segment, picking up where the second left off, has a slope negative to the
  second's, but is half as long.
16  The fourth line segment is horizontal, continuing where the third line segment concluded and
  going until the EOL threshold is reached.
17 end

```

3.1.1 Finding the Peaks

The peaks in $b'(x)$ are assumed to occur in its last 200 data points, so we take the maximum value attained over those points, recording the cycle number after break-in where it occurred (the “peak location”) and taking care to discard outliers to avoid significant disruption to our approximation. To predict these peaks using only data recorded before the cycle of prediction, we compared the information about the peaks with the average value of $b'(x)$ over these cycles (again, after break-in; called the “averages”). It was also later discovered that a gain in accuracy, especially for longer-lasting batteries, is achieved if the batteries were distinguished by charge policy. Specifically, in the manner of a decision tree, those following a one-step charge policy (see the “Methods” section in [4]) were separated from the others, and the peak locations for these were predicted using the corresponding charge rates.

A more clearly linear relation was seen when peak locations were plotted against these averages on a log-log scale; therefore, logarithms of averages were used to predict logarithms of peak locations (see Fig. 5).

Once the series of line segments approximating $b'(x)$ is obtained, antiderivatives are used to estimate $b(x)$, with the associated constants chosen such that $b(x)$ is continuous. Fig. 6 shows some examples of the resulting approximations, both of $b'(x)$ and of the capacity decay profiles. As expected, the closer our approximation to $b'(x)$, the more accurate our prediction of cycle life.

3.2 Other Function Families

If either of the graphs in any of the Fig. 4 plots is vertically reflected, it is evident how closely $b'(x)$ resembles a multiple of the capacity profile or some linear combination

Figure 5: Linear fits of peaks and locations with averages and charge policy.

Figure 6: Approximations to $b'(x)$ (left, in red) and the capacity decay profile (right, in orange).

Function Family Name	Formula	Bounds
Logistic	$\frac{cy_0}{ky_0 + (c - ky_0)e^{-cx}}$	$0 < k < 0.1,$ $-0.02 < c < 0.01,$ $-0.1 < y_0 < 0$
Reciprocal	$\frac{y_0}{1 + ky_0x}$	$0 < k < 0.1,$ $-0.1 < y_0 < 0$
Inverse Square	$\frac{-a}{(x - c)^2} + b$	$0 < a < 5 \cdot 10^4,$ $0.1 < b < 1.1,$ $350 < c < 4 \cdot 10^3$

Table 2: Bounds used for SciPy’s `curve_fit` for some functional families.

thereof. Using a negative multiplier, then, the capacity (after translation, as with the exponential function family) may thus be approximated by a solution to one of the differential equations

$$\frac{y'}{y} = -ky \text{ or } \frac{y'}{y} = -ky + c,$$

which have, as respective solutions,

$$y = \frac{y_0}{1 + ky_0x},$$

a reciprocal function, and

$$y = \frac{cy_0}{ky_0 + (c - ky_0)e^{-cx}},$$

a logistic function, where y_0 is the initial value of the capacity data being modeled. (Here we assume $y_0 < 0$ and $k > 0$. Also, note that if $c > ky_0$, the logistic has a vertical asymptote.) This further justifies our choice of using these functions for curve-fitting.

Recall that Table 1 showed the form of the inverse-square function family as

$$\frac{-a}{(x - c)^2} + b;$$

the negative was affixed, with the assumption $a > 0$, to more easily fit the (in this case non-translated) capacity profile, which was generally decreasing.

Fits for these functions were attained through SciPy’s `optimize` package; in particular, using the `curve_fit` function, which fits arbitrary function families as specified by the user. Upper and lower bounds for the function family’s unknowns may be specified by the parameter bounds, and the function seeks for the optimal fit using nonlinear least-squares within these constraints. The bounds we settled upon for the function families this section concerns are listed in Table 2.

4. Final Results

For all regressors except the SVR, we omit one battery (of the remaining 121) to cross-validate our predictions. We then construct the model using the remaining batteries, predict

the cycle life for the omitted battery, and repeat these steps for all batteries. For the SVR, we use a train-test split having either one or two test sets. The resulting predictions for the SVR (for both training and test sets) are then combined with those for all other regressors in a weighted average. This is what we use as our final prediction and is compared with the true values of the cycle lives. The average percent error and RMSE are calculated from this comparison.

To recap, the five regressors we have been using (having discarded the cubic) are the four functional forms (exponential, logistic, reciprocal, inverse-square) and the SVR. We use a weighted average of these to get the most reliable prediction; i.e., with minimal RMSE. While the functional form regressors yield the same result for every run, the variable train-test split employed for the SVR means that there isn't a tuple of weights that optimizes the prediction each time, and instead we look for one that tends to give us the best predictions on average.

Basic grid search methods were used to tune the following hyperparameters, leading to our deciding upon the values succeeding in parentheses, educated guesses for what would produce an ensemble model that was both reasonably accurate and early in making predictions:

- cycle number of prediction (350),
- cycle number of first data point (after “break-in”) used in prediction (50),
- number of cycles to skip in computing derivative divide (50),
- multiplier determining t_1 , the first threshold (0.95).

These were kept constant while we varied the weights to use for the weighted average. A Monte Carlo simulation was run on the weights, with those having RMSE under a certain predetermined threshold recorded. It was readily found that those weighted averages zeroing the weights for the reciprocal and inverse-square predictors gave optimal RMSE and these regressors were subsequently dropped. The remaining three yielded low RMSE values over a wide range of weight 3-tuples; means of the distributions of weights were calculated to suggest the following weights for general usage of the resulting ensemble: for the exponential family, 55%; the logistic family, 15%; the SVR, 30%.

Figure 7: (a) Final prediction error cone. (b) Histograms of average percent error and RMSEs after 200 model runs.

Inspecting the predictions made by the exponential model independently, it is seen that the “crude” approximations (Fig. 6) of $b'(x)$ described above give improved results

and are therefore incorporated in the ensemble model. Running the ensemble model 200 times, it is found, each time, that a better average percent error and worse RMSE than the corresponding averages of model runs in [3]’s Table 3 is attained. Our improvements noted above in chapter 3, however, reduce the deficit in average RMSE from roughly 60 cycles (initial results) to approximately 15 cycles (final results; see Fig. 7).

5. Conclusions & Future Work

This work gives insight into previously unconsidered methods of predicting battery cycle life; the technique described herein may likely be expanded to batteries of other types and subjected to other conditions. The pattern seen in the derivative $b'(x)$ of the exponent in the exponential function, for instance, may be enlightening in future work. One may consider analyzing various expressions of the derivative of capacity decay to gain an understanding of the type(s) of differential equations it satisfies or approximates, and thus apply appropriate curve fits. A weighted average of individual regressors may give a suitably accurate prediction for actual cycle life. Our results are also accurate enough to show that our methods may serve as desirable in validating others.

Other techniques, such as Fourier series, or a recurrent neural network such as an LSTM, may be more efficient at approximating the capacity decay derivative, some form thereof, or even the original capacity decay profile itself. Functional data analysis, including functional PCA, may also be a promising avenue of research.

Our major difficulty in dealing with this dataset was the problem of differentiating the longer-lasting batteries (i.e., lasting more than 1500 cycles) from others using only early cycles. Ensembles combining previously used methods could comprise other branches to include in the decision tree (e.g., separating by batch number), a replica of [4]’s “elastic net,” finite-difference methods, a particle filter, Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), etc.

References

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